

Providing access to cost-efficient, replicable,
safe and flexible CCUS

CO2 Transporte and Storage as a Service

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About ACCSESS

If CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) is to become a relevant, large-scale technology for cutting carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, several barriers need to be addressed, and its deployment must be accelerated.

ACCSESS works to address key challenges to the successful implementation of CCS across Europe: namely, challenges related to CO₂ capture, CCS chains, and societal acceptance. The project focuses on four industrial sectors with the potential to drastically reduce CO₂ emissions by implementing CCS: waste-to-energy, pulp and paper, cement, and biorefineries.

ACCSESS started in May 2021. Its consortium consists of 18 partners from eight different European countries.

www.projectaccess.eu

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CO₂ Transport and Storage as a Service

Image courtesy: [Northern Lights Project](#)

About this document:

This document provides a possible approach to establishing CO₂ transport and storage services as part of a comprehensive Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) strategy, encapsulated in the construct of 'Neutral Solution Packages' (NSP). The 'Neutral' in NSP reflects its design for broad applicability across diverse contexts, without being tied to a specific site. 'Solution' indicates a strategic response that effectively tackles the challenges of CCS implementation, while 'Packages' conveys the comprehensive and all-inclusive nature of the guidelines. The primary audience for this document includes policymakers, stakeholders in the energy and energy intensive industry sectors, and city administrators who are instrumental in driving the transition to low-carbon urban environments. Exploring the crucial role of cities in the logistics of captured CO₂, particularly through ports and river transport, this case aims to offer a broader understanding of the larger-scale processes involved in CO₂ transport. The focus here is on the pivotal role of the CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure in supporting a wide range of CCS initiatives, critical to achieving significant urban carbon emissions.

Description:

The essence of a CCS hub is collective transport and storage infrastructure that supports a range of different emitters, CO₂ capture operators and possibly several hubs to CO₂ storage sites. Transport and storage operators are responsible for transporting the captured CO₂ by pipeline, ship, or other means to the storage site, where they inject it into the subsurface geology.

Challenge/Aim:

The main objective is to assist industrial emitters in preventing unavoidable emissions from entering the atmosphere, and to provide a safe and permanent storage solution for captured CO₂. The main challenge here is to establish a CCS value chain within Europe with a potentially growing capacity to store CO₂ as demand grows.

Solution:

Projects that require CO₂ shipping by means of transport include receiving already captured and conditioned CO₂ from industrial sources and transporting it from the capture sites to an onshore terminal (for now in Europe: on the Norwegian west coast). From there, it will be transported by pipeline or specially designed ships to an offshore storage location and injected for permanent storage below the seabed of the North Sea. Across the entire transport chain, multiple modes of transport are possible depending on the specific chain (pipeline, ships, trains, trucks, or barges).

Within the EU's Project of Common Interest, European Commission chose 14 projects on CO₂ transport and storage, where in each project specifics of the infrastructure chain differ (Global CCS Institute, 2023). In the example of the Northern Lights project, that is part of the listed projects, CO₂ is transported by ship to a storage site on the Norwegian continental shelf. In its first phase, Northern Lights estimates to develop a storage capacity of 1.5 million tonnes CO₂ per annum. This will be done by developing an open infrastructure to transport captured CO₂ by ship to an intermediate terminal located in western Norway, to then be sent to its permanent storage located in a reservoir 2.600m under the seabed (Northern Lights, n.d.).

Implementation Process:

Image courtesy: [CCS value chain from CO₂ capture to permanent storage](#)

The phases and milestones of the CO₂ storage life cycle, including the various permits for the correct implementation of such a project, are as follows:

The first **assessment** phase includes the assessment of the storage potential, defining the storage sites and their related exploration requirements, followed by a review of the exploration permit applications. At the end of this phase, the project should be awarded an **Exploration Permit**.

The second **Characterisation** phase starts with a review of the storage permit applications, making sure that compliance with all requirements of the directives is ensured in consideration with the opinions of the Commission. The end of this stage is marked by obtaining a **storage permit**.

The third **development** phase is in charge of the oversight of any baseline monitoring & reporting necessary for the successful implementation of the project, coming up with monitoring and corrective measures (CM) plans, and approving of any updates related to them. Afterwards, the **injection process** may begin.

The fourth **operation** phase involves regular inspections, review of storage permits, oversight of the monitoring & reporting process, and approval of the monitoring and CM plan updates. Corrective measures must be taken if needed, and periodic adjustments to financial security are of great importance. At the end of this phase, two possible paths are identified: (1) Authorisation to close, which starts with the approval of a definitive post-closure plan (*circumstance 1*) or (2) Decision to close site after permit withdrawal (*circumstance 2*).

The next **Post-Closure/ Pre-Transfer** phase depends on the path occurring: *Circumstance 1* involves continuation of the inspections, oversight of the monitoring & reporting process, and the like before approval of the monitoring/CM plan updates. *Circumstance 2*, on the other hand, takes on operator responsibilities for monitoring, reporting, CM, risk assessment, and modelling, and **transfers the responsibility** for operation to the to the country where the storage site is located.

Finally, the last **post-transfer** phase involves long-term stewardship by EU Member States, which will be responsible for monitoring to detect leakages, for conducting corrective measures, as needed, and for surrendering allowances, as needed. Depending on the specific agreements, EEA and EFTA countries may be involved.

Implementation time required:

- Evaluation and exploration phase after receiving a survey permit: up to 3 years.
- Evaluation of the phase of CO₂ storage potential after receiving an exploration permit: up to 10 years.
- Development and operation phase after receiving an exploitation permit: up to 50 years.
- Shutdown and post-operation phase: up to 20 years.
- Transfer of responsibility phase: up to 30 years.

Regulations and laws:

The implementation of such projects must comply with certain regulations and laws both on the national and international level. The EU-Emission Trading System (EU-ETS) Directive 2003/87 applies so far to such projects as it sets the European Emission ETS, which establishes the scheme for greenhouse emission allowance within the EU. This directive is amended by the newer Directive (EU) 2023/959 of 10 May 2023. Furthermore, EU Directive 2009/31 establishes the EU legal framework for cross-border transport and storage of CO₂, which also proves relevant for such infrastructure projects. However, since there are only a few projects of this kind under construction in Europe (the Longship by Northern Lights to be operational in 2024 and the project lead by Porthos approved in 2023), regulations have not yet been adapted to cover all phases of the initiative, leaving loopholes and uncertainties regarding the responsibilities over possible CO₂ leaks between the different CCS value chain actors.

A good example is the Norwegian interpretation of the EU's Monitoring and Reporting Regulations, which states that carbon capture operators will be able to deduct CO₂ from their emissions accounts *once* it has been transferred from the CO₂ transport ship to the reception

terminal. The European Commission has agreed with this interpretation of the law. However, this implies that a carbon capture operator cannot deduct CO₂ from its emissions account before it has been transferred from the ship to the reception terminal and the storage operator has issued a confirmation of the quantity of CO₂ that was delivered. Furthermore, according to the EU ETS directive, the capture operator will not have approved deductions from its emissions for any CO₂ leaks during transport, suggesting that the capture operators are left with the financial risk of CO₂ leakage from a ship they are not operating themselves.

A solution to this problem could be found in additional bilateral agreements between carbon capture and carbon storage operators, which state that the carbon capture operator will not be responsible for CO₂ during the transport phase and therefore regulate the matter legally, as this particular subject is not covered by the EU-ETS directive.

Financial details based on a specific use-case:

Financial Detail	Input
Initial investment for implementation	Approx. 7 billion NOK (2019)
Annual operational costs	Approximately 250 million NOK (2019) Operation of 2x ship, operation of onshore facilities, 1 x injection well

Barriers to development:

With respect to regulatory challenges, storage liabilities are a key risk for transport and storage operators when it comes to legally defined responsibilities. CO₂ storage liability should be made clear in advance, answering the question of which party is responsible at each stage of injection, monitoring, and long-term stewardship. Regulations on how risk is shared and eventually transferred to government should also be included, and current regulations should be updated to include the non-ETS sectors.

Furthermore, in some projects, conditioned CO₂ is transported using trucks and ships in this CCS chain, while current regulations have assumed that transportation is done solely through pipelines. Complications regarding international cross-border CO₂ transport also pose a challenge: At what point is the responsibility for a CO₂ leak during transport transferred from one country to another? Bilateral agreements between the countries may be a potential solution here. There is also possible social and political resistance since there is ‘no guarantee’ that a project will be successful from a climate change perspective.

Regarding storage facilities, challenges may arise as the transport and storage operator will need to invest upfront to quantify the storage capacity and derisk it for potential customers (e.g., geological derisking may require shooting seismic and drilling wells. Upfront investment in derisking storage will make it much easier to scale CCUS hubs, but few policymakers have focused on this to date.) Transport costs and long-term storage options pose additional barriers.

Permits for the zoning plan, consent for pipelines, and offshore licences are needed. The operator will also need to identify the specifications (around purity and pressure) of CO₂ to be delivered to the transport and storage operator. Looser specifications make post-capture compression and purification cheaper for emitters, but impurities in carbon dioxide - such as water, nitrogen, SO_x, NO_x, carbon monoxide, hydrocarbons, and mercury - can have major

implications, such as corrosion, safety etc, for carbon dioxide transportation and storage infrastructure.

Therefore, these questions must be resolved before the start-up of any commercial CCS chain.

Enablers to development:

1. Government support is helpful in removing potential barriers to development, such as regulatory challenges.
2. Trailblazing new public-private partnership models and navigating a path to a more efficient regulatory process.
3. The government bears additional cross-chain risks related to the interface between the subprojects, it protects private partners from weaknesses in other links of the chain (e.g., if one of the capture projects were to fail, Northern Lights could find other CO₂ suppliers, or if Northern Lights were to fail, the capture projects could likely find a different storage provider without facing catastrophic loss).

Citizen Engagement and City-Company Collaboration:

Public participation is vital to the success of the CO₂ transport and storage project, with the aim of building community support, addressing concerns and ensuring effective communication. Here are typical strategies in more detail:

- **Information Sessions and Workshops:** Organise events to educate the public about CCS technology, its environmental benefits, safety measures, risks, and challenges ensuring that the information is accessible and easy to understand.
- **Stakeholder consultations:** Regular engagement with local residents, businesses, environmental groups, and local authorities to collect their feedback, address concerns, and incorporate their insights into project planning.
- **Educational Collaborations:** Partner with schools and universities to introduce educational programmes and materials on CCS, facilitating a deeper understanding of its role in reducing climate change.
- **Transparent communication:** Maintain open channels for sharing regular project updates, challenges, and progress, ensuring transparency in operations and decision-making processes.
- **Public forums and Discussion Panels:** Host events with experts, community leaders, and project representatives to facilitate open discussions, allowing the community to express their opinions and seek clarifications.
- **Online Engagement:** Use social networks, websites, and online forums to reach a wider audience, particularly targeting younger demographics, and provide interactive platforms for information sharing and feedback.
- **Feedback Mechanisms:** Implement various tools such as surveys, comment forms, or online forums to collect and address public opinions, adapting project strategies based on this feedback.

- **Community Benefits Programme:** Develop initiatives that offer direct benefits to the local community, such as creating job opportunities, improving local infrastructure, or offering educational scholarships, to demonstrate the project's commitment to local development and sustainability.

Lessons learnt/ Impact:

Regarding technical and legal aspects, attention must be paid to e.g., fish farms in the sea during dredging, filling activities, and blasting operations. Timely management of land acquisition is necessary to address additional requirements imposed by landowners, as their authorisation is required for building application processes if the land has not been acquired. Additionally, zoning plan approval is required before sending building applications. Additional considerations concern potential cultural heritage sites that, if present, may incur additional costs and processes. Another important legal information refers to projects dealing with offshore CO₂ pipelines, as they are also the subject of the same building application process as onshore construction ones.

Some organisational aspects worth considering focus on detailed timelines and stakeholder management, which are essential for successful project implementation. It is important to set up meeting series to inform before main application processes start up to get early feedback and implement regular meeting arenas under construction. Also, different types of application have varying handling times (e.g., one-step application or framework, and start-up application). Project managers should be aware that the consent application to may have a long handling time of approximately six months and is conducted in two steps.

Advice for replication:

For implementation of further CCS logistics projects, it would be advisable to work on increasing public acceptance for CCS technology, e.g., through education, and to develop new storage sites, including evaluating onshore options, to simplify transport and enable CCS projects for inland plants.

SWOT-Analysis:

Strengths	Weaknesses
Broad applicability: Serves various industries, enhancing versatility and market reach.	Regulatory gaps: Lacks comprehensive legal frameworks, leading to potential liabilities and uncertainties.
Advanced CCS technology: Using cutting-edge carbon capture and storage technology for efficient CO ₂ handling.	High capital requirement: Requires substantial upfront investment, making it financially demanding for new entrants.
Responsibility transfer: Transfers the liability of CO ₂ from emitters to storage operators, assuring professional handling.	Implementation Complexity: Involves intricate processes and requires significant expertise and resources for execution.
Climate change mitigation: Plays a crucial role in reducing atmospheric CO ₂ , aligning with global sustainability goals.	Tech-Dependence: Heavily depends on the success and reliability of evolving CCS technologies.
Opportunities	Threats
Climate action: The growing global demand for sustainable solutions presents significant	Public opposition: Faces a potential backlash over environmental and safety concerns, impacting public acceptance.

market opportunities for involved stakeholders along the value chain.	
Tech evolution: Continuing advances in CCS tech could streamline processes and reduce costs.	Regulatory changes: Future legal changes could affect the operational feasibility and financial models.
Policy incentives: Potential for supportive government policies, including subsidies and tax benefits.	Emerging alternatives: Competition from new, possibly more cost-effective emission reduction technologies.
Inter-industry collaboration: Opportunities for joint ventures with a variety of sectors, expanding usage scenarios.	Geopolitical challenges: Cross-border transport and international relations can influence operational dynamics.

In summary, while CCS offers immense potential in combatting climate change, proactive measures to address weaknesses, adapt to external factors, and foster international collaboration are imperative for its success in the evolving landscape. Ever-changing environmental and regulatory context is especially relevant for CCS logistics projects as they involve multiple countries with potentially different legislative background and conditions for operations.

Addressed SDGs:

Media files and further reading:

Title	Author	Year	Link
Directive 2003/87/EC establishing a scheme for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading.	European Parliament & Council	2003	EUR-Lex - 32003L0087 - EN - EUR-Lex (europa.eu)
Directive 2023/959 amending Directive 2003/87/EC	European Parliament & Council	2023	EUR-Lex - 32023L0959 - EN - EUR-Lex (europa.eu)
Directive 2009/31/EC on the geological storage of carbon dioxide	European Parliament & Council	2009	EUR-Lex - 32009L0031 - EN - EUR-Lex (europa.eu)
The EU legal framework for cross-border CO ₂ transport and storage in the context of the requirements of the London Protocol	Commission analysis services	2022	EU-London Protocol Analysis paper_final0930.pdf (europa.eu)

Transport and storage operators.	The CCUS HUB	Transport & storage operators, The CCUS Hub (ogci.com)
Long-ship carbon capture and storage in Norway's North Sea	Canadian Climate Institute	Longship Carbon Capture and Storage in Norway's North Sea - Canadian Climate Institute
Responsibility for CO ₂ in the chain	CCS Norway 2022	Responsibility for CO₂ in the chain - CCS Norway
About the Longship project	Northern Lights	About the Longship project, Northern Lights (norlights.com)
Porthos CO ₂ Transport & Storage	Porthos	Port of Rotterdam CO₂ Transport Hub and Offshore Storage

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Northern Lights. (u.d.). Hämtat från Northern Lights: <https://norlights.com/>